

EFFECTS OF SOLE AND AMENDED PLANT RESIDUES ON SEED NUTRIENTS CONTENT AND GROWTH OF AMARANTHUS (*Amaranthus viridis L.*)

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ABSTRACT

A study was conducted in southwest Nigeria on the effect of woodash, sawdust, ground cocoahusk, spentgrain and ricebran, used ordinarily or amended with goat, pig and poultry manure on seed nutrients contents and growth parameters of amaranthus (*Amaranthus viridis L.*). Twenty organic fertilizer treatments were compared to the control (no treatment) and 4000kg/ha NPK fertilizer. Application of 6t/ha plant residues to soil increased seed N, P, K, Ca and Mg contents, and plant height, leaf area and root growth. Spentgrain, woodash and cocoahusk gave higher values of seed N and growth parameters. NPK fertilizer gave better value of plant height compared with the plant residues, but spentgrain gave better leaf area compared to NPK fertilizer. The residues significantly increased seed Ca and Mg contents unlike in case of Fertilizer. Amendment of plant residues with animal manure increased their effect on growth of amaranthus. The seed N, P, and Ca content growth of amaranthus increased with addition of plant residues.

KEYWORDS: Amaranthus, plant residues, sole and amended, seed nutrients and growth parameters

INTRODUCTION

Small scale cultivators of vegetable crops in humid tropical countries use the same piece of land continuously, and after some years the crops suffer from nutrients deficiency, especially those of nitrogen and phosphorus leading to poor growth and low yield. Where common NPK fertilizer is used, the crops also suffer from lack of nutrients not supplied such as Ca and Mg. This is apart from the problems of scarcity and high cost of chemical fertilizer. Therefore, there is need to investigate into locally available, cheap organic fertilizers for vegetable production. The use of plant residues in vegetable production has not received research attention, although decomposing plant residues are known to release appreciable amounts of nutrients into the soil. For example, Kumar *et al* (1999) found that application of groundnut haulin, maize stover and mustard stover contributed considerable amount of nutrients which improved nutrient uptake by rice and soil organic matter N, P and K contents.

Amaranthus viridis L. is a common vegetable growth for its edible leaves. Also the seeds may be fried for consumption. In this study, plant residues such as woodash, ground cocoahusk, ricebran, spentgrain and sawdust, applied sole or amended with type of animal manure, were tried as fertilizers for amaranths. Their effects on nutrients composition and growth parameters of amaranthus were investigated.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Experiments were carried out at Akure in the rainforest zone of southwest Nigeria on a sandy loam soil. The surface soil (0-15cm) has a pH (water) of 5.1, organic matter 0.53%, 0.02% N, 4.6mg/kg extractable P and 0.08 mmol/kg extractable K, 0.1mmol/kg exchangeable Ca and 1.12 mmol/kg exchangeable Mg (Folorunso, 1999). The lowly fertile soil had been cropped continuously for 10 years.

Twenty plant residue treatments, sole and amended, NPK fertilizer (400kg/ha 15-15-15 NPK) and control (no treatment) were applied to amaranthus soil. The live plant residues were woodash, ground cocoahusk, ricebran, spentgrain (sorghum based brewery waste) and sawdust. The plant residues were applied sole at 6t/ha and were combined with each of goat manure, pig manure and poultry manure at the rate of 3t/ha each. The 22 treatments were replicated three times one each of four consecutive crops at the same site using a randomized complete block design. The size of each of the 6 plots was 16m². The fertilizer and manure were incorporated into soil seven days before planting. Prior processing of the residues was done to allow fast decomposition in the soil.

Seeds of amaranthus were hand drilled in rows that were 30 cm apart (20 rows, per plot) at the rate of 7.5 kg/ha. Seeds were mixed with equal volume of sand for even spread. Germination took place five days after planting at 10 days after planting seedlings were thinned to a population of about 535332 plants per hectare (i.e. 212 plants per 16m² plot).

One hundred and sixty plants were selected on each plot. Plant parameters such as height and leaf area were measured at second, third and fourth weeks after planting. At senescence. The selected plants were uprooted for the determination of root length, and were oven-dried at 70°C for 24 h. The inflorescence was removed and the extracted seeds were milled into powdered form. The milled seed samples were digested with nitro-perchloric – sulphuric acid mixture (AOAC, 1970). P was determined colorimetrically by the vanadomolybdate method, and Ca and Mg were determined by atomic absorption spectrophotometer. N was estimated using the kjeldahl method. The mean seed analysis and plant growth data for the treatments and four crops of Amaranthus are compared using the Duncan multiple range test at 5% level.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The sole and amended plant residues increased amaranthus seed N (Table 1) P (Table 2), Ca (Table 3) and Mg (Table 4) contents, and plant height (Table 5) leaf area (Table 6) and root length (Table 7) relative to the control.

Among the plant residues, spentgrain, woodash, and cocoahusk, gave better values of growth parameters of amaranthus such as plant height (Table 5), leaf area (Table 6) and root length (Table 7). They also had higher seed N status (Table 1). The woodash also gave the higher seed Ca and Mg values. The sawdust and ricebran which gave the least values of growth parameters had the least seed N values, although they had the highest values of seed P. therefore, it appeared that the availability of N to the crop mostly dictated the growth of performance of crop growth in southwest Nigeria soils (Ojeniyi, 1984; Moyin-Jesu, 2003).

The spentgrain mostly enhanced root growth of amaranthus (Table 7). This agrees with the observation (Folorunso, 1999; Moyin-Jesu, 2008) that its soil recorded the least bulk density. This should have enhanced water uptake. Hence spentgrain gave the highest values for plant height and leaf area.

The NPK fertilizer gave the best value for plant height compared with the plant residues, but spentgrain gave better leaf area compared to fertilizer. The best plant height of amaranthus treated with NPK fertilizer is consistent with its highest seed N value. However the plant residues used ordinarily or amended, significantly increased ($P > 0.05$) seed Ca and Mg values unlike in case of NPK fertilizer.

The amendment of plant residues with goat, pig, and poultry manure increased the plant height (Table 5), leaf area (Table 6) and root length (Table 7). This agrees with the fact that the amendment increased seed N content, except in case of cocoahusk, However, the amendment of cocoahusk also increased seed P content. These observations indicate the importance of N and P for the growth of the vegetable crop. The types of animal manure had lower C:N compared to the plant residues (Folorunso, 1999) and should have enhanced the decomposition of the residues thereby hastening release of N and probably P.

The seed N, P and Ca contents and plant height, leaf area and root length increased with addition of sole and amended plant residues up to the fourth crop. However, the seed Mg content dropped after the third application of residues. Therefore there was cumulative effect of residue additions on amaranthus growth and N and P contents.

CONCLUSION

It is concluded that application of plant residues to soil increased availability of Ca and Mg, to amaranthus thereby enhancing its growth. The amendment of the residues with types of animal manure enhanced their effects on amaranthus growth. Therefore the plant residues were effective as fertilizer for amaranthus.

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TABLE 1: The effect of plant residues plus manure on % seed Nitrogen under the four crops of Amaranthus

S/N	Treatments	1 st	2 nd	3 rd	4 th	MEAN
1	Control	0.02a	0.03a	0.07a	0.03a	0.04a
2	NPK 15-15-15	2.78o	3.57u	4.22t	4.33t	3.73r
3	Wood Ash (Sole)	2.52k	2.86k	3.572r	3.71n	3.17l
4	Wood Ash + Goat Dung	2.58lm	3.14q	3.312kl	3.82o	3.21m
5	Wood Ash + Pig Dung	2.36f	3.15qr	3.56q	3.83op	3.23mn
6	Wood Ash + Poultry manure	2.53kl	3.25s	3.56q	3.95qr	3.23op
7	Cocoa Husk (Sole)	2.63mn	3.26st	3.848s	3.92q	3.41pq
8	Cocoa Husk + Goat Dung	2.42ghi	2.87kl	3.402n	3.50jkl	3.05k
9	Cocoa Husk + Pig Dung	2.38fgh	2.75fy	3.256q	3.34fg	2.93ij
10	Cocoa Husk + Poultry manure	2.50fghi	2.95op	3.308k	3.59m	3.06k
11	Rice Bran (Sole)	0.136	0.17b	0.12b	0.13b	0.14b
12	Rice Bran + Goat Dung	0.14cd	0.18c	0.13bc	0.16e	0.15c
13	Rice Bran + Pig Dung	0.14cd	0.19d	0.144e	0.15d	0.15cd
14	Rice Bran + Poultry manure	0.14cd	0.18c	0.13d	0.14c	0.18bc
15	Spent Grain (Sole)	1.41fghi	1.86cd	1.39m	1.49jk	1.54f
16	Spent Grain + Goat Dung	2.37fg	2.73f	3.23f	3.33f	2.9fi
17	Spent Grain + Pig Dung	2.4hij	2.90Klmno	3.424p	4.18s	3.2no
18	Spent Grain + Poultry manure	2.44hij	2.77fgh	3.29hi	3.39gh	2.97j
19	Saw Dust (Sole)	0.44hij	0.87klmn	1.41no	1.50jkl	1.05e
20	Saw Dust + Goat Dung	1.40fghi	1.78fghi	1.91kl	2.40hi	1.87g
21	Saw Dust + Pig Dung	1.39fgh	1.79ghij	1.98h	2.49jk	1.9fgh
22.	Saw Dust + Poultry manure	1.40fghi	1.79ghij	2.30j	2.45ij	1.98j

Treatment means within each group or column followed by the same letters are not significantly different from each other using DMRT at 5% level.

TABLE 2: The effect of plant residues plus manure on % seed P under the four crops of Amaranthus

S/N	Treatments	1 st	2 nd	3 rd	4 th	MEAN
1	Control	0.0238a	0.0418a	0.0524a	0.0494a	0.04185a
2.	NPK 15-15-15	0.0696n	0.1136m	0.44m	0.154n	0.1204kl
3	Wood Ash (Sole)	0.0856r	0.143r	0.1804q	0.1912r	0.15005o
4.	Wood Ash + Goat Dung	0.083q	0.1498t	0.1894s	0.215t	0.1593p
5.	Wood Ash + Pig Dung	0.12518v	0.2164v	0.2746v	0.2844v	0.2252r
6	Wood Ash + Poultry manure	0.0668lm	0.104k	0.1352l	0.1524kl	0.1162k
7	Cocoa Husk (Sole)	0.0402c	0.0696d	0.088d	0.0962d	0.073d
8.	Cocoa Husk + Goat Dung	0.0716o	0.1248p	0.1578p	0.1664p	0.0130d
9	Cocoa Husk + Pig Dung	0.0502g	0.0862g	0.1076g	0.1138g	0.1302m
10.	Cocoa Husk + Poultry manure	0.0564h	0.0932h	0.1168h	0.128h	0.0806h
11	Rice Bran (Sole)	0.095u	0.1622u	0.20528u	0.2238u	0.1716q
12	Rice Bran + Goat Dung	0.0874t	0.1372q	0.1914t	0.1818q	0.1495n
13	Rice Bran + Pig Dung	0.066i	0.1138mn	0.1444no	0.1544no	0.1197kl
14	Rice Bran + Poultry manure	0.0808p	0.1146n	0.1442mn	0.1532m	0.1232lm
15	Spent Grain (Sole)	0.0328b	0.0534b	0.067b	0.0778b	0.05775b
16	Spent Grain + Goat Dung	2.37fg	2.73f	3.23f	3.33f	2.9fi
17	Spent Grain + Pig Dung	0.041d	0.0664c	0.0778c	0.092c	0.0692c
18	Spent Grain + Poultry manure	0.048ef	0.0826f	0.106f	0.113f	0.0874f
19.	Saw Dust (Sole)	0.086s	0.148s	0.1872r	0.1958s	0.1543op
20	Saw Dust + Goat Dung	0.058i	0.0974i	0.1228i	0.1328i	0.1028hi
21	Saw Dust + Pig Dung	0.060j	0.1016j	0.1284j	0.1386j	0.1072j
22.	Saw Dust + Poultry manure	0.04de	0.0766e	0.0948e	0.10312e	0.07963e

Treatment means within each group or column followed by the same letters are not significantly different from each other using DMRT at 5% level.

TABLE 3: The effect of plant residues plus manure on % seed Ca under the four crops of Amaranthus

S/N	Treatments	1 st	2 nd	3 rd	4 th	MEAN
1	Control	0.04794a	0.04794a	0.04794a	0.0479a	0.04793a
2.	NPK 15-15-15	0.0406t	0.0082s	0.0948s	0.098lmno	0.0604b
3	Wood Ash (Sole)	0.804u	0.9612v	1.0164v	1.417t	1.04965t
4.	Wood Ash + Goat Dung	0.8382v	0.8632u	0.9608u	1.279qr	0.9853s
5.	Wood Ash + Pig Dung	0.6306s	0.6916r	0.7662r	1.238pq	0.831613q
6	Wood Ash + Poultry manure	0.4726m	0.5236m	0.598klm	1.040jkl	0.65855kl
7	Cocoa Husk (Sole)	0.5102o	0.5638o	0.6306n	1.334s	0.7597o
8.	Cocoa Husk + Goat Dung	0.5866q	0.6662q	0.7484q	1.078lm	0.7698p
9	Cocoa Husk + Pig Dung	0.42141i	0.4606i	0.523e	0.811cd	0.554g
10.	Cocoa Husk + Poultry manure	2.50fghi	2.95op	3.308k	3.59m	3.06k
11	Rice Bran (Sole)	0.6076r	0.7452t	0.8454t	1.185q	0.8458r
12	Rice Bran + Goat Dung	0.456k	0.50041	0.566jk	1.165p	0.67175m
13	Rice Bran + Pig Dung	0.5326p	0.5896p	0.629p	0.996hij	0.6943n
14	Rice Bran + Poultry manure	0.3698ef	0.4024f	0.4596f	0.953gh	0.5462f
15	Spent Grain (Sole)	0.3526d	0.383cd	0.4374d	0.907fg	0.52e
16	Spent Grain + Goat Dung	0.487n	0.5476n	0.6382o	0.897ef	0.6425k
17	Spent Grain + Pig Dung	0.3648e	0.399de	0.461g	0.885e	0.5275e
18	Spent Grain + Poultry manure	0.4392j	0.4728j	0.546j	0.959fgh	0.6043j
19.	Saw Dust (Sole)	0.3862g	0.4128g	0.4788h	0.978hi	0.5639h
20	Saw Dust + Goat Dung	0.3096c	0.342c	0.4074c	0.810c	0.4673d
21	Saw Dust + Pig Dung	0.4596kl	0.491k	0.576jkl	1.083lmn	0.6524kl
22.	Saw Dust + Poultry manure	0.285b	0.3134b	0.370b	0.742b	0.4276c

Treatment means within each group or column followed by the same letters are not significantly different from each other using DMRT at 5% level.

TABLE 4: The effect of plant residues plus manure on the plant height of Amaranthus between 2 to 4 weeks after planting under different crops (cm)

S/N	Treatments	1 st	2 nd	3 rd	4 th	MEAN
1	Control	0.08a	0.08a	0.02a	0.02a	0.02b
2.	NPK 15-15-15	0.01a	0.07a	0.07a	0.04a	0.47a
3	Wood Ash (Sole)	0.28u	0.43v	0.66u	0.59v	0.49r
4.	Wood Ash + Goat Dung	0.25t	0.38u	0.60t	0.54u	0.45q
5.	Wood Ash + Pig Dung	0.20pq	0.31r	0.48pq	0.47r	0.37o
6	Wood Ash + Poultry manure	0.17lm	0.25m	0.40m	0.40n	0.30k
7	Cocoa Husk (Sole)	0.20p	0.29p	0.46o	0.43pq	0.35n
8.	Cocoa Husk + Goat Dung	0.22r	0.34ts	0.54r	0.47s	0.80s
9	Cocoa Husk + Pig Dung	0.1314h	0.197hi	0.31114h	0.346ij	0.2451fg
10.	Cocoa Husk + Poultry manure	0.16kl	0.21ij	0.39kl	0.34k	0.28i
11	Rice Brain (Sole)	0.14bh	0.157c	0.42b	0.1b	0.43p
12	Rice Bran + Goat Dung	0.15j	0.23k	0.36j	0.3g	0.27
13	Rice Bran + Pig Dung	0.5326p	0.5896p	0.629p	0.996hij	0.6943n
14	Rice Bran + Poultry manure	0.12d	0.17e	0.27d	0.32de	0.22de
15	Spent Grain (Sole)	00.12de	0.17ef	0.27de	0.32f	0.22de
16	Spent Grain + Goat Dung	0.18n	0.25mn	0.42n	0.38m	0.31kl
17	Spent Grain + Pig Dung	0.1c	0.17d	0.26c	0.31cd	0.21c
18	Spent Grain + Poultry manure	0.16k	0.23kl	0.38k	0.37l	0.29j
19.	Saw Dust (Sole)	0.13f	0.19gh	0.30f	0.34i	0.24f
20	Saw Dust + Goat Dung	0.10b	0.16c	0.25bc	0.31d	0.20b
21	Saw Dust + Pig Dung	0.141	0.19g	0.34i	0.3gh	0.25g
22.	Saw Dust + Poultry manure	0.1284fg	0.1432b	0.3064g	0.2894c	0.2169cd

Treatment means within each group or column followed by the same letters are not significantly different from each other using DMRT at 5% level.

TABLE 5: The effect of plant residues plus manure on the plant height of Amaranthus between 2 to 4 weeks after planting under different crops (cm)

S/N	Treatments	1 st	2 nd	3 rd	4 th	MEAN
1	Control (No fertilizer)	4.50a	4.48a	4.50a	4.49a	4.49a
2.	NPK 15-15-15	28.22q	43.34u	52.30v	54.30u	44.54v
3	Wood Ash (Sole)	12.1ef	15.66f	22.05f	24.10fg	18.48f
4.	Wood Ash + Goat Dung	16.49l	21.47jk	35.55o	37.34n	27.71o
5.	Wood Ash + Pig Dung	18.55no	22.32l	32.71n	33.61m	26.80n
6	Wood Ash + Poultry manure	0.17lm	0.25m	0.40m	0.40n	0.30k
7	Cocoa Husk (Sole)	15.46jk	27.34p	39.74q	41.23p	33.80p
8.	Cocoa Husk + Goat Dung	18.32n	2.91lm	29.54kl	30.10j	25.22j
9	Cocoa Husk + Pig Dung	20.97p	26.69o	37.88op	37.90q	30.36p
10.	Cocoa Husk + Poultry manure	27.81u	37.86q	44.02t	45.04q	38.68st
11	Rice Brain (Sole)	7.11b	12.43cd	16.23c	18.41q	13.55c
12	Rice Bran + Goat Dung	13.59h	18.84h	26.78i	28.90i	22.03h
13	Rice Bran + Pig Dung	14.35i	21.19j	27.59j	30.10j	23.31j
14	Rice Bran + Poultry manure	15.32j	23.20mn	29.10k	35.50l	24.78k
15	Spent Grain (Sole)	17.60m	23.16mn	30.22lm	30.88jk	25.47lm
16	Spent Grain + Goat Dung	23.58r	31.79r	40.66r	48.15s	35.05r
17	Spent Grain + Pig Dung	26.32t	36.46t	43.15s	46.16r	38.02s
18	Spent Grain + Poultry manure	28.80v	37.37s	48.16u	58.30t	41.41u
19.	Saw Dust (Sole)	9.46c	11.70b	14.71b	15.21b	12.77b
20	Saw Dust + Goat Dung	10.74d	12.06c	16.99cd	17.60c	14.35d
21	Saw Dust + Pig Dung	11.80e	15.11e	19.68e	21.11e	16.93e
22.	Saw Dust + Poultry manure	12.97g	11.86g	22.23fg	23.82f	18.97fg

Treatment means within each group or column followed by the same letters are not significantly different from each other using DMRT at 5% level.

TABLE 6: The effect of plant residues plus manure on the leaf area (cm²) of Amaranthus under four crops.

S/N	Treatments	1 st	2 nd	3 rd	4 th	MEAN
1	Control (No fertilizer)	2.50a	2.53a	2.50a	2.49a	2.51a
2.	NPK 15-15-15	10.64hi	16.643l	24.673ij	32.90h	21.20i
3	Wood Ash (Sole)	8.31e	13.91ef	22.38gh	27.62g	18.06g
4.	Wood Ash + Goat Dung	14.83k	20.74l	28.98l	35.96jk	25.13l
5.	Wood Ash + Pig Dung	15.35lm	22.4o	29.49m	47.26lm	28.64p
6	Wood Ash + Poultry manure	17.39o	25.59q	31.35n	47.01r	30.84r
7	Cocoa Husk (Sole)	8.92f	12.23d	21.96q	25.85e	17.24f
8.	Cocoa Husk + Goat Dung	14.12j	21.18m	32.94o	37.41mn	26.41n
9	Cocoa Husk + Pig Dung	17.83opq	25.69q	34.80q	42.84q	30.29q
10.	Cocoa Husk + Poultry manure	20.03r	27.24r	36.81r	47.04r	32.78s
11	Rice Bran (Sole)	5.14b	7.91b	1.62b	14.38b	9.76b
12	Rice Bran + Goat Dung	10.27gh	14.90g	17.82e	19.79d	15.70d
13	Rice Bran + Pig Dung	14.08j	18.12j	24.19i	32.96h	22.34j
14	Rice Bran + Poultry manure	17.86op	22.80op	25.49k	36.27kl	25.61lm
15	Spent Grain (Sole)	16.62n	21.94	34.19p	39.02o	27.95o
16	Spent Grain + Goat Dung	24.80s	40.96s	55.32s	81.99s	50.77t
17	Spent Grain + Pig Dung	26.34t	42.71t	65.48t	98.22t	58.19u
18	Spent Grain + Poultry manure	35.34u	52.71u	84.33u	126.49u	74.72v
19.	Saw Dust (Sole)	5.94c	8.42c	13.73c	17.50c	11.40c
20	Saw Dust + Goat Dung	7.71d	13.50e	16.60d	26.31ef	16.03de
21	Saw Dust + Pig Dung	10.11g	15.17gh	18.47f	33.10i	19.21h
22.	Saw Dust + Poultry manure	15.21l	18.58jk	21.94g	35.40j	22.78jk

Treatment means within each group or column followed by the same letters are not significantly different from each other using DMRT at 5% level.

TABLE 7: The effect of plant residues plus manure on the root length (cm) Amaranthus under four crops.

S/N	Treatments	1 st	2 nd	3 rd	4 th	MEAN
1	Control (No fertilizer)	3.21a	3.74a	3.40a	3.54a	3.47a
2.	NPK 15-15-15	10.00d	15.37bc	14.15b	14.35b	13.47d
3	Wood Ash (Sole)	11.71e	14.43b	19.67e	21.41e	16.81e
4.	Wood Ash + Goat Dung	13.46g	16.84d	21.83fg	22.40f	18.63f
5.	Wood Ash + Pig Dung	15.34lm	17.07de	22.12h	23.12g	19.41h
6	Wood Ash + Poultry manure	17.44op	23.20o	29.56s	30.81rs	25.25pq
7	Cocoa Husk (Sole)	13.57gh	19.73g	22.83ij	25.31jk	20.36i
	Cocoa Husk + Goat Dung	14.03hi	20.14i	24.90mn	27.24n	21.58kl
9	Cocoa Husk + Pig Dung	15.03kl	23.13o	26.34p	29.31q	23.45no
10.	Cocoa Husk + Poultry manure	15.16l	23.55op	25.47o	28.29p	23.12n
11	Rice Bran (Sole)	7.46b	9.84b	16.83d	17.40c	12.88b
12	Rice Bran + Goat Dung	13.40g	19.87gh	22.43hi	26.10l	20.45i
13	Rice Bran + Pig Dung	16.80n	21.87lm	23.86k	26.45lm	22.25m
14	Rice Bran + Poultry manure	17.30o	22.86n	24.49lm	27.42no	23.02n
15	Spent Grain (Sole)	18.36q	21.70l	26.87q	30.45r	24.35p
16	Spent Grain + Goat Dung	19.50r	25.77q	27.17qr	31.23st	25.92r
17	Spent Grain + Pig Dung	21.70s	26.42r	30.86t	33.81u	28.20s
18	Spent Grain + Poultry manure	22.48t	27.07s	31.60u	34.44v	28.90t
19.	Saw Dust (Sole)	8.02bc	9.93b	15.77c	18.32d	13.01c
20	Saw Dust + Goat Dung	12.02ef	17.73f	21.69f	23.83h	18.82fg
21	Saw Dust + Pig Dung	14.18ij	20.75j	22.77ij	24.82i	20.63ij
22.	Saw Dust + Poultry manure	14.88k	21.04jk	24.14kl	25.09ij	21.29k

Treatment means within each group or column followed by the same letters are not significantly different from each other using DMRT at 5% level.